

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GRAPHITE EPOXY COMPOSITES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this investigation was to evaluate the effects of elevated temperatures on the mechanical properties of graphite fiber reinforced organic matrix composites. The tensile, compressive, and shear strengths and moduli, as well as the Poisson ratios of Fiberite 976 resin and Fiberite T300/976 unidirectional graphite epoxy composite were measured at temperatures ranging from 75 to 350°F. The longitudinal and transverse strengths, moduli, and Poisson ratios of the composite were also calculated from the known values of the resin and fiber properties using the "rule of mixture" and Tsai-Hahn formulas. The measured and calculated composite properties were compared, and the accuracies of the aforementioned formulas were assessed.

INTRODUCTION

Although fiber-reinforced organic matrix composites are now widely used in land, sea, and aerospace structures, there is concern that the mechanical properties of such materials decrease at elevated temperatures. Hence, to realize the full potential of composites, their mechanical behavior at high temperatures must be known. Therefore, the objectives of this investigation were to determine the changes in the mechanical properties of a graphite epoxy composite in the range 75 to 350°F, and to assess the accuracies of selected micromechanic relationships in predicting the mechanical properties at these temperatures. To achieve these objectives, first the tensile, compressive, and shear properties of Fiberite 976 resin and Fiberite T300/976 graphite epoxy composite were measured. Second, the mechanical properties of the composite were calculated by the "rule of mixture" and the Tsai-Hahn formulas, and the properties thus calculated were compared to data generated in this study.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The test specimens were cut from panels made of unidirectional tape or of pure resin. The composite and resin panels were cured by the temperature cycle shown in Figure 1.

The dimensions of the composite test specimens are shown in Figure 2. Fiberglass tabs were placed on the tensile and compressive specimens. The tensile tests were performed according to an ASTM Standard [1]. The compressive tests were performed with a Celanese test fixture [2]. The shear properties were measured by the Iosipescu method [3]. In the tensile tests the strains were measured with an extensometer in the direction of the load and by a strain gauge normal to the load. In the compression and shear tests the strains were measured by two strain gauges mounted on each specimen. All the tests were performed at the strain rate of 0.25 in./in.-min.

The pure resin test specimens were cut from 10 in long, 8 in wide, and 0.12 in thick plates made from commercially available Fiberite 976 resin. The resin, received in "hot melt" form, was melted at 212°F and outgassed at this temperature for 90 minutes. The melted resin was then poured into an aluminum mold which had been preheated to 212°F. The mold containing the resin was placed into an oven whose temperature was regulated to achieve the desired degree of cure (see Figure 1).

The resin specimens were tested in tension, compression, and shear in the same manner as the composite specimens.

Figure 1. Temperature cycle used in preparing the specimens.

Figure 2. Geometries of the tensile, compressive and shear specimens. All units in inches.

RESULTS

The measured tensile, compressive, and shear strengths and moduli, as well as the Poisson ratio of the Fiberite 976 resin are given in Table 1. Each value in this table is the average of six data. Examination of the data in Table 1 revealed that the changes with temperature of each property can be approximated by the expression

$$P = P_o \left(\frac{T - T_r}{T_o - T_r} \right)^n \quad (1)$$

where P is the property under consideration (strength, modulus, or Poisson's ratio) at temperature T , P_o is the value of the property at temperature T_o . Here we chose T_o to be room temperature ($T_o = 75^\circ\text{F}$). T_r is a reference temperature, and n is a constant with a value between 0 and 1 ($0 \leq n \leq 1$). The values of T_r and n must be obtained by fitting Eq. (1) to the data. The T_r and n values obtained by a least square fit to the data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1
Measured properties of Fiberite 976 resin* and the constants T_r and n
used in Eq. (1). (The data shown are the average of six tests.)

Temperature (°F)	75	250	300	350	T_r	n
Tensile modulus, E_{mt}	0.548	0.393	0.360	0.315	716	1
Compressive modulus, E_{mc}	0.680	0.480	0.410	0.347	526	0.72
Shear modulus, † E_{ms}	0.216	0.156	0.142	0.122	716	1
Tensile strength, S_{mt}	7.89	5.08	4.55	4.38	636	1
Compressive strength, S_{mc}	52.3	39.1	36.8	32.9	812	1
Shear strength, S_{ms}	4.60	3.54	3.13	3.20	874	1
Poisson's ratio, ν_m	0.270	0.258	0.260	0.286		0

*The moduli are in Msi and strengths in Ksi.

†The shear moduli were calculated by $E_{ms} = E_{mt}/[2(1 + \nu_m)]$.

Figure 3. The variations in tensile properties with temperature of Fiberite T300/976 composite. Error bars represent spread in the data. Calculations are by the equations given in Table 4 and the properties in Tables 1 and 4.

Figure 4. The variations in compressive properties with temperature of Fiberite T300/976 composite. Error bars represent spread in the data. Calculations are by the equations given in Table 3 and the properties in Tables 1 and 4.

Figure 5. The variations in shear properties with temperature of Fiberite T300/976 composite. Error bars represent spread in the data. Calculations are by the equations given in Table 3 and the properties in Tables 1 and 4.

Figure 6. The variations in the longitudinal and transverse Poisson ratios with temperature of Fiberite T300/976 composite. Error bars represent spread in the data. Calculations are by the equations given in Table 4 and the properties in Tables 1 and 4.

TABLE 2
Measured properties of Fiberite T300/976 composite*
and the constants T_r and n used in Eq. (1)
(The data shown are the average of six tests.)

Temperature (°F)	75	250	300	350	T_r	n
Longitudinal tensile modulus	22.7	22.4	22.6			0
Longitudinal compressive modulus	24.2	23.2	24.0	23.1		0
Transverse tensile modulus	1.32	1.14	1.19	1.12	1904	1
Transverse compressive modulus	1.88	1.51	1.40	1.35	994	1
Longitudinal shear modulus	1.01	0.87	0.78	0.63	368	0.17
Longitudinal tensile strength	220	222	201			0
Longitudinal compressive strength	231	208	190	171	400	0.16
Transverse tensile strength	7.11	4.23	3.71	3.50	568	1
Transverse compressive strength	36.7	32.1	26.2	25.4	448	0.29
Longitudinal shear strength	16.3	13.7	12.1	10.6	404	0.24
Longitudinal Poisson's ratio	0.228	0.232	0.216			0
Transverse Poisson's ratio [†]	0.0133	0.0118	0.0114		1904	1

*The moduli are in Msi and strengths in Ksi.

[†]The transverse Poisson ratios were calculated by $\nu_T = E_{T1}\nu_L/E_{Lt}$.

The measured mechanical properties of Fiberite T300/976 graphite epoxy composites as functions of temperature are shown in Figures 3-6 and Table 2. Each data represented by a circle in these figures is the average of six tests.

The data in Figures 3-6 indicate that, as expected, the matrix-dominated properties vary more with temperature than the fiber-dominated properties. Interestingly, the variations with temperature of the properties of the composite can also be represented by an expression such as given by Eq. (1). The constants n and T_r are different, of course, for the resin and for the composite. The values of n and T_r for the composite are also included in Table 2. Equation (1), together with these constants, may be used to estimate the mechanical behavior of structures at elevated temperatures.

Although it is of interest to determine the changes in mechanical properties with temperature, our main objective was to determine whether or not at elevated temperatures the strengths, moduli, and Poisson's ratios can be predicted from the known values of the resin and fiber properties. Therefore, the strengths, moduli, and Poisson's ratios of the composite were calculated by the "rule of mixture" [4] and the Tsai-Hahn [5] formulas. These relationships are summarized in Tables 3 and 4. The composite strengths, moduli, and Poisson's ratios calculated by these relationships (using the resin and fiber properties given in Tables 1 and 4) are included in Figures 3-6.

The results in Figures 3-6 show that the simple "rule of mixture" expressions predict well the longitudinal tensile strengths and moduli, the longitudinal Poisson ratios, and the longitudinal compressive moduli. The models proposed by Tsai and Hahn describe closely the transverse tensile and compressive strengths and moduli, the transverse Poisson ratios, the longitudinal compressive strengths, and the longitudinal shear strengths and moduli.

The success of the Tsai-Hahn expressions in predicting the mechanical properties may be partly due to the fact that these expressions include two adjustable constants (η and K , in Tables 3 and 4). Here, the values of the constants were selected to provide a best fit to the data. Once the values of these constants were chosen, the Tsai-Hahn relationship yielded the appropriate values of the properties over the temperature range 75 to 350°F.

In conclusion, the results described herein show that changes in the mechanical properties of composites with temperature can be predicted from the resin and fiber properties. For the Fiberite T300/976 graphite-epoxy system the rule of mixtures and the Tsai-Hahn expressions yield acceptable results. Accordingly, these expressions could be used in the design of composite structures exposed to high temperatures.

TABLE 3
Micromechanic equations used in calculating the composite properties
 (Symbols are defined in Tables 1 and 4.)

	Rule of Mixture	Tsai-Hahn
Longitudinal tensile modulus	$E_{Lt} = v_f E_{Lf} + v_m E_{mt}$	
Longitudinal compressive modulus	$E_{Lc} = v_f E_{Lf} + v_m E_{mc}$	
Transverse tensile modulus	$\frac{1}{E_{Tt}} = \frac{v_f}{E_{Tf}} + \frac{v_m}{E_{mt}}$	$\frac{1}{E_{Tt}} = \frac{1}{v_f + \eta_{Tt} v_m} \left[\frac{v_f}{E_{Tf}} + \frac{\eta_{Tt} v_m}{E_{mt}} \right]$
Transverse compressive modulus	$\frac{1}{E_{Tc}} = \frac{v_f}{E_{Tf}} + \frac{v_m}{E_{mc}}$	$\frac{1}{E_{Tc}} = \frac{1}{v_f + \eta_{Tc} v_m} \left[\frac{v_f}{E_{Tf}} + \frac{\eta_{Tc} v_m}{E_{mc}} \right]$
Longitudinal shear modulus	$\frac{1}{E_{Ls}} = \frac{v_f}{E_{sf}} + \frac{v_m}{E_{ms}}$	$\frac{1}{E_{Ls}} = \frac{1}{v_f + \eta_{Ls} v_m} \left[\frac{v_f}{E_{sf}} + \frac{\eta_{Ls} v_m}{E_{ms}} \right]$
Longitudinal tensile strength	$S_{Lt} = v_f S_{Lf} + v_m S_{mt}$	
Longitudinal compressive strength		$S_{Lc} = \frac{\beta}{\pi} S_{Ls}$
Transverse tensile strength		$S_{Tt} = \frac{1+v_f(1/\eta_{Tt}-1)}{K_t} S_{mt}$
Transverse compressive strength		$S_{Tc} = \frac{1+v_f(1/\eta_{Tc}-1)}{K_c} S_{mc}$
Longitudinal shear strength		$S_{Ls} = \frac{1+v_f(1/\eta_{Ls}-1)}{K_s} S_{ms}$
Longitudinal Poisson's ratio	$\nu_L = v_f \nu_f + v_m \nu_m$	
Transverse Poisson's ratio	$\nu_T = \frac{E_{Tt}}{E_{Lt}} \nu_L$	$\nu_T = \frac{E_{Tt}}{E_{Lt}} \nu_L$

TABLE 4
Properties used in the calculations

Fiber

Longitudinal modulus, $E_{Lf} = 33.4$ Msi	[Union Carbide]
Transverse modulus, $E_{Tf} = 2.20$ Msi	[back-calculation]
Longitudinal shear modulus, $E_{sf} = 1.10$ Msi	[back-calculation]
Longitudinal tensile strength, $S_{Lf} = 320$ Ksi	[back-calculation]
Poisson's ratio, $\nu_f = 0.203$	[back-calculation]

Composites

Fiber volume fraction, $v_f = 0.66$	[present data]
Matrix volume fraction, $v_m = 0.34$	[present data]
Constant in the Tsai-Hahn equation, $\beta = 49$	[fit present data]
Transverse tensile stress partitioning factor, $\eta_{Tt} = 0.41$	[fit present data]
Transverse compressive stress partitioning factor, $\eta_{Tc} = 0.19$	[fit present data]
Shear stress partitioning factor, $\eta_s = 0.11$	[fit present data]
Transverse tensile stress concentration factor, $K_t = 2.3$	[fit present data]
Transverse compressive stress concentration factor, $K_c = 5.4$	[fit present data]
Shear stress concentration factor, $K_s = 1.8$	[fit present data]

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